

Structural Design and Analysis of a CubeSat-based Rover for Hyperspectral Camera Imaging

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Abstract: As interest in Moon exploration grows, low-cost scientific missions are being explored to make Moon exploration more accessible to universities and small research institutions. Traditional moon rovers require significant resources, limiting access to moon surface exploration. This study is part of the LUNEX and EuroMoonMars initiative, focusing on advancing low-cost lunar exploration technologies. One promising solution is to adapt the standardized low-cost systems developed for low-Earth orbit (LEO), which endure similar environmental conditions, and extend their qualifications for Moon exploration. The CubeSat platform, widely regarded as the most successful standardized platform for LEO low-cost missions in recent decades, can potentially be adapted for low-cost Moon surface exploration.

This study introduces a CubeSat-based rover design which utilizes a standard 3U CubeSat as the baseline, with hyperspectral camera as the primary payload for moon surface observation. A CubeSat-based rover is a compact, modular robotic vehicle which directly integrates CubeSat technology onto a mobile rover platform, enabling it to conduct scientific experiments on the Moon surface. The proposed rover design aims to extend CubeSat technology to meet the requirements of Moon surface missions, including extreme temperature fluctuations, Moon landing impact load, and Moon regolith interactions under low gravity. A comprehensive analysis of the rover's performance under simulated Moon surface conditions is also presented in this study, including wheel-soil interaction analysis, rover stability analysis, and structural finite element analysis under load conditions from launch to landing and operating on the Moon. Experimental tests under simulated lunar conditions were also conducted on the CubeSat-based rover design and are presented in this study to validate the structural analysis results and the design's functionality. The results of these analyses and experimental tests demonstrate that a CubeSat-based rover can meet the requirements of a small-scale moon surface observation mission.

Additionally, comparison with past moon surface exploration missions shows the cost-effectiveness of the CubeSat-based rover platform. The study also provides useful insights into the feasibility of adopting CubeSat-based rovers as low-cost platforms for lunar surface exploration missions.

Prototype Rover Design. The prototype rover design, as shown in Figure 1, is based on the 3U CubeSat form factor, leveraging its compact dimensions (10 x 10 x 34 cm) following CubeSat Design Specification [1] and standardized interface to facilitate rapid development and integration of additional subsystems to extend its function as surface exploration lunar rover. Rover wheel is sized according to the methodology proposed by Alhammadi [2]. Material selection and rover shape design choices are conducted after studying Neurospace CubeRover journal [3].

Figure 1: Prototype Rover Model

Structural Analysis. A comprehensive structural assessment of the CubeSat-based rover was conducted using finite element analysis (FEA) to ensure survivability from launch through lunar surface operations, following ESA Structural General Requirement [4]. The rover structure, composed primarily of aluminum 7075-T6, was subjected to various mechanical loads encountered during launch, landing, and surface deployment. Key analyses included quasi-static load, random vibration, thermal stress, and shock response spectrum, which are critical for validating the rover structural performance. An example of structural simulation result is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Rover launch shock event FEA Result

These simulations were further validated by mobility testing, vibration test, and shock test conducted on a prototype. Rover Mobility Test were conducted on sandy surface to simulate loose Lunar regolith as shown in Figure 3. Vibration and shock tests were conducted using a shaker table and drop-test rig under simulated lunar surface gravity and terrain profiles. The results confirmed the structural robustness and mechanical integrity of the CubeSat-based rover, supporting its suitability for deployment in lunar environments.

Figure 3: Rover Mobility Test on sandy surface.

References: Use the brief numbered style common in many abstracts, e.g., [1], [2], etc. References should then appear in numerical order in the reference list, and should use the following abbreviated style:

[1] Alicia Johnstone. (2022) *CubeSat Design Specification Rev 14.1*. [2] M. Alhammedi. (2022) *"Lunar Rover Wheels Design & Analysis"*, Khalifa University, 2022. [3] M. U., L F., M. M. (2023) *Application of CubeSat Technologies for Research and Exploration*, *Advances in Astronautics Science and Technology*, 57–72. [4] ESA. (2008), *"ECSS-E-ST-32C: Structural general requirements,"*.